

ISTANBUL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY ★ MARITIME FACULTY

**COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF ALTERNATIVE FUEL USAGE ON SHIPS
CRUISING IN BALTIC CAPESIZE INDEX C5 ROUTE FROM THE
ENVIRONMENTAL AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY PERSPECTIVES**

DESIGN PROJECT

Ahmet Ali ATALAY

Department of Marine Engineering

JUNE 2023

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**Ahmet Ali ATALAY
(820200703)**

Department of Marine Engineering

Thesis Advisor: Prof. Dr. Yasin ARSLANOĞLU

JUNE 2023

İSTANBUL TEKNİK ÜNİVERSİTESİ ★ DENİZCİLİK FAKÜLTESİ

**ÇEVRESEL VE ENERJİ VERİMLİLİĞİ PERSPEKTİFLERİNDEN BALTİK
CAPESIZE İNDEKSİ C5 ROTASINDA SEYREDEN GEMİLERDE
ALTERNATİF YAKIT KULLANIMININ KARŞILAŞTIRMALI
DEĞERLENDİRMESİ**

BİTİRME TEZİ

**Ahmet Ali ATALAY
(820200703)**

Gemi Makineleri İşletme Mühendisliği

Tez Danışmanı: Prof. Dr. Yasin ARSLANOĞLU

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FOREWORD

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

FOREWORD	iv
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vi
ABBREVIATIONS	ix
SYMBOLS	xiii
LIST OF TABLES	xv
LIST OF FIGURES	xvii
SUMMARY	xix
ÖZET	xxi
1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. BALTIC CAPE SIZE INDEX	7
2.1 Baltic Capesize Index Routes	8
2.2 Selection of Baltic Capesize Index C5 Route.....	10
3. REGULATIONS ON SHIP SOURCED EMISSIONS IN INDUSTRY	13
3.1 Obligations Related to The Implementation of Regulations	14
3.2 Requirements for Control of Individual Type of Emissions	15
3.3 Energy Efficiency Requirements	18
3.4 Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) Ratings.....	21
4. REGULATIONS ON SHIP SOURCED EMISSIONS IN INDUSTRY	25
4.1 Analysis of Alternative Fuel Availability in BCI C5 Route.....	30
4.2 Alternative Fuel Adaptation Study on BCI C5 Route	32
4.2.1 Vessels	34
4.2.2 Fuel	35
4.2.3 Bunkering.....	37
5. CALCULATING AND COMPARISON OF EMISSION VALUES ON BALTIC CAPE SIZE INDEX C5 ROUTE	40
5.1 Methodology.....	40
5.2 Data Review.....	40
5.3 Calculating Reference Vessel Specifications and Consumptions.....	41
5.4 Emission Factors.....	43
5.5 Calculating CII For Heavy Fuel Oil	43

5.6 Calculating CII For Methanol	44
5.7 Calculating CII For Liquefied Natural Gas	44
5.8 Scaling One Year Emissions	44
6. CONCLUSION.....	47
REFERENCES.....	51
CURRICULUM VITAE.....	55

ABBREVIATIONS

AE	: Auxiliary Engine
AR5	: Fifth Assessment Report, IPCC
BDN	: Bunker Delivery Note
BCI	: Baltic Capesize Index
CCS	: Carbon Capture and Storage
CEAS	: Computerized Engine Application System, MAN
CFC	: Chlorofluorocarbon
CII	: Carbon Intensity Indicator
CNG	: Compressed Natural Gas
CCUS	: Carbon Capture, Utilization (or Usage) and Storage
DCS	: Data Collection System, IMO
DME	: Dimethyl Ether
DO	: Diesel Oil
DWT	: Deadweight Tonnage
ECA	: Emission Control Area
EEDI	: Energy Efficiency Design Index
EGCS	: Exhaust Gas Cleaning System
EGR	: Exhaust Gas Recirculation
EIAPP	: Engine International Air Pollution Prevention, Certificate
ENSO	: El Niño Southern Oscillation
EEXI	: Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index
FO	: Fuel Oil
FC	: Fuel Consumption
F-Gas	: Fluorinated Gas
GHG	: Greenhouse Gas
GWP	: Global Warming Potential
GWP100	: 100-year GWP
HCFC	: Hydrochlorofluorocarbons
HFC	: Hydrofluorocarbons

HFO	: Heavy Fuel Oil
HPDF	: High Pressure Gas Injection, Engine
HSSC	: Harmonized System of Survey and Certification
HVAC	: Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IAPP	: International Air Pollution Prevention, Certificate
IEA	: International Energy Agency
IEE	: International Energy Efficiency, Certificate
IMO	: International Maritime Organization
IPCC	: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LBM	: Liquid Biomethane
LBSI	: Lean-Burn Spark Ignited, Engine
LCV	: Lower Calorific Value
LNG	: Liquefied Natural Gas
LPG	: Liquefied Petroleum Gas
LPDF	: Low Pressure Dual-Fuel, Engine
MARPOL	: International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships
MCR	: Maximum Continuous Rating
MDEA	: Methyl Diethanolamine
MDO	: Marine Diesel Oil
ME	: Main Engine
MEA	: Monoethanolamine
MEPC	: Marine Environment Protection Committee
MGO	: Marine Gas Oil
NCEI	: National Centers for Environmental Information
NOAA	: National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
ODS	: Ozone Depleting Substances
PFC	: Perfluorocarbons
PM	: Particulate Matter
PS1-6	: Projection Scenario from 1 to 6
PZ	: Piperazine
RPM	: Revolutions per Minute
SBCC	: Ship-Based Carbon Capture

SCR	: Selective Catalytic Reduction
SECA	: SO _x Emission Control Area
SEEMP	: Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan
SFC	: Specific Fuel Consumption
SFOC	: Specific Fuel Oil Consumption
SGC	: Specific Gas Consumption
SNG	: Synthetic Natural Gas
SOLAS	: International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea
SPOC	: Specific Pilot Oil Consumption
TtW	: Tank to Wake
UNCLOS	: United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
VLSFO	: Very Low Sulphur Fuel Oil
VOC	: Volatile Organic Compounds
WHR	: Waste Heat Recovery
WtT	: Well to Tank
WtW	: Well to Wake

SYMBOLS

a, b, c	: Parameters for required EEDI, EEXI and CII
C	: Capacity for CII in DWT
C_F	: CO ₂ emission conversion factor from fuel consumption
C_{PM}	: PM emission conversion factor from fuel consumption
C_{SO_x}	: SO _x emission conversion factor from fuel consumption
CH_3OH	: Methanol
CH_4	: Methane
CO_2	: Carbon Dioxide
CII_{Ref}	: CII reference line
D	: Distance travelled for CII in miles by land
DO_e	: Equivalent DO consumption, converted from others with LCV
i	: Engine load percentage
m_{CH_4}	: Mass of methane slip in g/kWh
m_{PM}	: Mass of PM emissions for LNG in g/kWh
$MtCO_2e$	: Million tonne equivalent CO ₂
$MTCO_2e$	: Metric tonne equivalent CO ₂
n	: Engine speed in RPM
NH_3	: Ammonia
NO_x	: Nitrogen Oxides
N_2O	: Nitrous Oxide
P	: Power in kW
$PM_{2.5}$	: PM that are or lower than 2.5 microns
PM_{10}	: PM that are or lower than 10 microns
$rCII$	: Required CII
SF_6	: Sulphur Hexafluoride
SO_x	: Sulphur Oxides
t	: Time in hours
x, y, z	: Percentage reduction factors for EEDI, EEXI and CII, respectively

S%*m/m* : Percentage mass by mass for the sulphur content in fuels

LIST OF TABLES

	<u>Page</u>
Table 1.1 : Greenhouse gas summary.	2
Table 2.1 : Baltic Capesize Index BCI main routes definations.	9
Table 4.1 : Fundamental marine alternative fuels.	28
Table 5.1 : Dataset provided by AIS Provider and calculated based on average of data for different vessel classes from AIS Provider averaging real-world data shared by the Green corridor consortium.	39
Table 5.2 : Reference vessel.....	40
Table 5.3 : Calculated alternative fuel consumption for roundtrips.....	40
Table 5.4 : Designated emission factors for CO_2	41
Table 5.6 : Scaled-up CO_2 emission values for alternative fuel usage scenario in one year.....	43
Table 5.7 : Scaled-up emission values for alternative fuel usage scenario in one year	43

LIST OF FIGURES

	<u>Page</u>
Figure 1.1 : Climate Change Strategy Timeline.	5
Figure 3.1 : MARPOL Emission Control Areas with their limitations.	16
Figure 3.2 : IMO NOx Tier emission standards for NECA.	17
Figure 3.3 : EEDI baseline referenced by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) and the attainable EEDI of the benchmark bulk carrier.	19
Figure 3.4 : Formulation of EEDI and EEXI.	21
Figure 3.5 : Required Annual Operational CII.	22
Figure 4.1 : Methanol Availability Map In Baltic Capesize Index C5 Route.....	29
Figure 4.2 : LNG supply map in China.....	30
Figure 4.3 : Timeline For Decarbonisation Iron Ore Shipping Between Western Australia and East Asia With Clean Ammonia.	32
Figure 4.4 : Focused Roadmap For Green Ammonia Supply For Green Corridor....	34
Figure 4.5 : Mainly Planned Bunkering Zones For Green Corridor.	37
Figure 6.1 : Scaled-up CO2 Emission Values In One Year.	44

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF ALTERNATIVE FUEL USAGE ON SHIPS CRUISING IN BALTIC CAPE-SIZE INDEX C5 ROUTE FROM THE ENVIRONMENTAL AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY PERSPECTIVES

SUMMARY

Anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with carbon dioxide (CO₂) being a primary contributor, have significantly disrupted the natural balance of the Earth's atmosphere, leading to global warming. This has resulted in persistent upward trends in annual global average temperatures and anomalies, leading to increasingly frequent and severe impacts of global warming. These consequences encompass adverse effects on human health, loss of biodiversity, water scarcity, food insecurity, and extreme climate events. Urgent and ambitious actions are therefore essential to mitigate these adverse impacts.

While maritime transportation is often considered an efficient and environmentally-friendly mode of transport, it is still responsible for emitting billions of tonnes of GHGs annually, placing it on par with some of the highest emitting countries worldwide. Moreover, projections indicate that the maritime industry's emissions could potentially increase by up to 250% by 2050. Hence, decarbonizing the maritime industry is crucial to achieving the ambitious goals outlined in the Paris Agreement.

The research in focus endeavors to shed light on the potential contributions of alternative fuels in reducing emission values and their practical implications for overall emission reduction efforts. By calculating and comparing the emissions associated with different fuel scenarios on the BCI C5 route, this study aims to provide valuable insights for decision-makers and industry stakeholders seeking sustainable maritime operations.

To conduct this research, comprehensive data on the energy consumption and emissions of capesize class ships on the BCI C5 route will be collected. This will include factors such as fuel consumption rates, voyage distances, and operational characteristics. The data will be used to calculate the emissions generated by these vessels when using marine diesel oil and when utilizing alternative fuels like ammonia, LNG, and hydrogen.

By quantifying the emission differences between traditional marine diesel oil and alternative fuels, the research aims to evaluate the potential environmental benefits and challenges associated with each fuel option. Additionally, the study will consider the economic viability, technological feasibility, and infrastructure requirements for the adoption of alternative fuels in the maritime sector.

In conclusion, this research addresses the critical issue of GHG emissions in the maritime sector, with a specific emphasis on vessels operating on the BCI C5 route. By conducting a comprehensive analysis of emission differences between traditional marine diesel oil and alternative fuels, the study contributes to our understanding of the effectiveness of alternative fuels in reducing emissions and promoting

sustainability within the global shipping industry. The findings of this research can inform policy development, guide strategic decision-making processes, and support efforts aimed at mitigating the environmental impacts associated with maritime transportation. Ultimately, these efforts are necessary to achieve a greener and more sustainable future for the maritime industry, while ensuring the efficient movement of goods on the BCI C5 route and beyond. The outcomes derived from the investigation unveiled that LNG, Methanol, and Hydrogen, which were examined as alternative fuel options within the purview of this study, exhibited substantially lower values in relation to significant emissions and carbon footprints compared to conventional marine fuels.

This research aims to comprehensively analyze and compare emission values in the context of alternative fuel usage scenarios for vessels operating on the Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) C5 route. Specifically, the study seeks to calculate and compare the emissions generated by capesize class ships when utilizing traditional marine diesel oil versus new-generation alternative fuels, including ammonia, liquefied natural gas (LNG), and hydrogen. The significance of this investigation lies in the fact that the BCI C5 route represents a substantial portion of global raw material trade, highlighting the need to reduce emissions from ships operating on this route.

ÇEVRESEL VE ENERJİ VERİMLİLİĞİ PERSPEKTİFLERİNDEN BALTIC CAPESIZE İNDEKSİ C5 ROTASINDA SEYREDEN GEMİLERDE ALTERNATİF YAKIT KULLANIMININ KARŞILAŞTIRMALI DEĞERLENDİRMESİ

ÖZET

Karbondioksit (CO₂) gibi insan kaynaklı sera gazı (GHG) emisyonları, Dünya'nın atmosferinin doğal dengesini önemli ölçüde bozarak küresel ısınmaya yol açmıştır. Bu durum, yıllık küresel ortalama sıcaklık ve anormalliklerde sürekli olarak artış trendlerine ve küresel ısınmanın giderek daha sık ve şiddetli etkilerine yol açmaktadır. Bu sonuçlar, insan sağlığı üzerinde olumsuz etkiler, biyoçeşitlilik kaybı, su kıtlığı, gıda güvensizliği ve aşırı iklim olayları gibi durumları içermektedir. Bu olumsuz etkileri azaltmak için acil ve iddialı önlemler önemlidir.

Deniz taşımacılığı genellikle verimli ve çevre dostu bir ulaşım şekli olarak kabul edilse de, yıllık olarak milyarlarca ton GHG emisyonu yayması nedeniyle dünyadaki en yüksek emisyon salan ülkelerle aynı seviyededir. Dahası, tahminlere göre, denizcilik endüstrisinin emisyonları 2050'ye kadar %250'ye kadar artabilir. Bu nedenle, denizcilik endüstrisinin karbonsuzlaştırılması, Paris Anlaşması'nda belirlenen iddialı hedeflere ulaşmak için önemlidir.

Bu odak araştırma, alternatif yakıtların emisyon değerlerinde azalmaya potansiyel katkılarını ve bunun genel emisyon azaltma çabaları üzerindeki pratik sonuçlarını açıklığa kavuşturmayı amaçlamaktadır. BCI C5 rotasındaki farklı yakıt senaryolarına bağlı olarak oluşan emisyonları hesaplayarak ve karşılaştırarak, bu çalışma sürdürülebilir denizcilik operasyonları arayan karar vericilere ve sektör paydaşlarına değerli bilgiler sağlamayı hedeflemektedir.

Bu araştırmayı yürütmek için, BCI C5 rotasında capesize sınıfı gemilerin enerji tüketimi ve emisyonlarıyla ilgili kapsamlı veriler toplanacaktır. Bu, yakıt tüketim hızları, seyahat mesafeleri ve operasyonel özellikler gibi faktörleri içerecektir. Bu veriler, deniz dizel yağı kullanıldığında ve amonyak, LNG ve hidrojen gibi alternatif yakıtların kullanıldığı durumlarda bu gemiler tarafından oluşturulan emisyonları hesaplamak için kullanılacaktır.

Geleneksel deniz dizel yağı ile alternatif yakıtlar arasındaki emisyon farklarını nicelendirerek, araştırma her bir yakıt seçeneği ile ilişkili potansiyel çevresel faydaları ve zorlukları değerlendirmeyi hedeflemektedir. Ayrıca, çalışma, denizcilik sektöründe alternatif yakıtların benimsenmesi için ekonomik geçerlilik, teknolojik uygunluk ve altyapı gereksinimlerini de dikkate alacaktır.

Sonuç olarak, bu araştırma, denizcilik sektöründeki GHG emisyonlarıyla ilgili önemli bir konuyu ele almaktadır, özellikle BCI C5 rotasında faaliyet gösteren gemiler üzerinde durulmaktadır. Geleneksel deniz dizel yağı ile alternatif yakıtlar arasındaki emisyon farklarının kapsamlı bir analizini yaparak, çalışma, küresel denizcilik

endüstrisinde emisyonları azaltma ve sürdürülebilirliği teşvik etme konusundaki etkinliği konusundaki anlayışımıza katkıda bulunmaktadır. Bu araştırmanın bulguları, politika geliştirme süreçlerine rehberlik edebilir, stratejik karar alma süreçlerini yönlendirebilir ve deniz taşımacılığıyla ilişkili çevresel etkileri hafifletmeye yönelik çabalara destek olabilir. Sonuç olarak, bu çabalar, BCI C5 rotası ve ötesinde mal hareketinin verimli bir şekilde gerçekleştirilmesini sağlarken, denizcilik endüstrisi için daha yeşil ve sürdürülebilir bir geleceğe ulaşmak için gereklidir. Çalışmanın bulguları ortaya koymuştur ki, çalışmada alternatif yakıt olarak ele alınan LNG, Methanol ve Hidrojen geleneksel denizcilik yakıtlarına alternatif olarak kayda değer emisyon ve karbon salınımı açısından daha düşük değerler ortaya koymuştur.

Bu araştırma, Baltık Capesize Index (BCI) C5 rotasında faaliyet gösteren gemiler için alternatif yakıt kullanım senaryoları bağlamında emisyon değerlerini kapsamlı bir şekilde analiz etmeyi ve karşılaştırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Özellikle, çalışma, capesize sınıfı gemilerin geleneksel deniz dizel yağı ile amonyak, sıvılaştırılmış doğal gaz (LNG) ve hidrojen gibi yeni nesil alternatif yakıtlar kullanıldığında oluşturduğu emisyonları hesaplamayı ve karşılaştırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Bu araştırmanın önemi, BCI C5 rotasının küresel hammadde ticaretinin önemli bir bölümünü temsil etmesinden kaynaklanmaktadır ve bu rotada faaliyet gösteren gemilerden kaynaklanan emisyonları azaltma ihtiyacını vurgulamaktadır.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Earth's thermal equilibrium relies on the intricate interplay between energy inflow and outflow within its planetary system. When solar radiation reaches the Earth's surface, it can either be reflected back into space or absorbed, leading to a thermal increment and subsequent release of infrared radiation into the atmosphere. Greenhouse gases in the atmosphere hinder the dissipation of heat, resulting in an elevated thermal state known as the greenhouse effect, vital for sustaining life. However, human-induced accumulation of greenhouse gases has caused transformative climate changes with detrimental consequences for human well-being and ecological systems (Basics of Climate Change | US EPA, 2021).

The irrefutable reality of climate change was demonstrated in the 2022 annual global climate change report by the NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI). Despite the presence of cold phase phenomena like El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO), 2022 ranked as the sixth warmest year since systematic global records began (Air Pollution Information System, 2020).

As global temperatures continue to rise, the impacts of climate change intensify in magnitude and frequency. Ecosystems worldwide undergo pervasive transformations, leading to species loss, increased disease prevalence, and catastrophic mortality events among flora and fauna. Extreme climatic phenomena such as droughts, wildfires, heatwaves, cyclones, and floods have far-reaching consequences, including population displacement, disrupted migratory patterns, and economic burdens from property damage and infrastructure impairment. The strains on food and forestry systems worsen, negatively affecting livelihoods, food security, and nutritional well-being for millions. Severe water scarcity looms over approximately half the world's population, with an estimated 3.3 billion individuals residing in countries highly vulnerable to climate change ((Bashmakov et al., 2022). Vulnerability is particularly pronounced in unplanned urban settlements, coastal regions, and mountainous areas, impacting the physical and mental well-being of affected individuals.

The atmosphere contains several primary greenhouse gases, including water vapor (H_2O), carbon dioxide (CO_2), methane (CH_4), nitrous oxide (N_2O),

chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons (PFCs), sulfur hexafluoride (SF_6), and ozone (O_3). Ozone-depleting substances (ODS) like HCFCs and CFCs have been phased out under the 1987 Montreal Protocol, replaced by HFCs and PFCs to protect the ozone layer. HFCs, PFCs, and SF_6 , known as fluorinated gases (F-gases), are regulated under the Kyoto Protocol. While the stratospheric ozone layer shields the Earth from harmful ultraviolet radiation, the fraction of ozone in the troposphere has dual effects, posing health risks as a toxic gas and exacerbating global warming. Anthropogenic tropospheric ozone primarily originates from photochemical smog, where nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) react to form ozone. Efforts to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions focus on reducing carbon dioxide (CO_2), methane (CH_4), nitrous oxide (N_2O), and fluorinated gases (F-gases), which accounted for the majority of emissions in 2019 (Yoro & Daramola, 2020).

Table 1.1 Greenhouse gas summary

Compound	Formula	Concentration (ppm)	Contribution (%)
Water vapor and clouds	H_2O	10–50,000	36874.11
Carbon Dioxide	CO_2	~400	8609.92
Methane	CH_4	~1.8	3096.79
Ozone	O_3	2–8	1177.41

Source:(European Environment Agency, 2021)

Among the various subsectors comprising the energy sector, notable contributors to greenhouse gas emissions include electricity and heating, accounting for 31.8% of emissions, and transportation, responsible for 14.3% of emissions. However, it is important to note that the electricity and heat subsector encompasses a diverse array of end-uses. These encompass residential and commercial heating applications, energy consumption within the agriculture and fishing sectors, as well as energy utilization within quarrying and mining activities, among others. In contrast, the transportation sector is characterized by a singular end-use focus, yet it stands out as one of the subsectors displaying substantial growth from 1990 to 2019, thus making it a significant contributor to emissions during this period (Climate Watch, 2019).

Maritime transportation stands as the cornerstone of the global economy and international trade system, facilitating the movement of an astounding 90% of global trade—a distinction that sets it apart from other modes of transportation. Its pivotal

role in transporting vital commodities such as raw materials, food, fuels, manufactured goods, and essential goods cannot be overstated. Without maritime transportation, the efficient transport, import, and export of these commodities would face severe limitations. Despite its indispensability, the shipping industry's contribution to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions was a modest 1.8% in 2019, with carbon dioxide (CO_2) accounting for approximately 3% of total annual anthropogenic GHG emissions (5 Facts about Country & Sector GHG Emissions, 2022). It is worth noting that shipping releases fewer CO_2 emissions per unit of cargo transported compared to other modes of transportation, as evidenced by the percentages. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that the industry still emits a staggering one billion tonnes of CO_2 annually, equivalent to the emissions of Germany, the world's seventh-largest emitter. The significant environmental impacts stemming from these emissions, particularly in coastal areas, coupled with projections indicating a potential growth of up to 250% in the industry by 2050, underscore the urgent need for improvements within the sector. Greenhouse gas emissions, predominantly in the form of CO_2 , primarily stem from the combustion of fossil fuels. The maritime industry is no exception, relying on heavy fuel oil (HFO) and marine diesel oil (MDO), along with their various derivatives, as widely utilized fossil fuels. Additionally, liquefied natural gas (LNG) serves as a common fuel source, particularly in LNG tankers. These hydrocarbon-based fuels, composed of hydrogen and carbon, undergo combustion in the presence of oxygen, leading to a chemical reaction that generates a range of combustion byproducts. In accordance with Lavoisier's law of conservation of mass, the total mass remains constant during a chemical reaction. Thus, the combustion of hydrocarbon-based fuels containing carbon gives rise to CO_2 emissions and other greenhouse gases, contingent upon the specific composition of the fuel (International Chamber of Shipping, 2022). Within the regulatory realm of the maritime shipping industry, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) took a significant step forward by incorporating a new annex, Annex VI – Prevention of Air Pollution from Ships, into the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL) in 1997. This annex came into effect in 2005 and marked the first instance of limitations imposed on pollutants such as sulfur oxides (SO_x), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), particulate matter (PM), and ozone-depleting substances (ODS) within the industry. Over time, these limitations have been progressively tightened. In 2010, the NOX Technical Code 2008 was implemented, which was subsequently amended in 2014 to regulate ship NO_x

emissions based on their engine speed and construction dates, categorized into different tiers. As for SO_x emissions, the initial limit of 4.5% mass by mass was revised to 3.5% in 2012 and further lowered to 0.5% in 2020. Additionally, specific regions designated as Emission Control Areas (ECAs) and SO_x Emission Control Areas (SECAs) have been established, subjecting ships operating within these areas to even more stringent limits. The expansion of these areas continues, with the recent inclusion of the Mediterranean Sea, set to take effect in 2025.

In 2013, another crucial regulatory development emerged with the introduction of a new chapter in Annex VI, addressing carbon dioxide (CO_2) and greenhouse gases (GHGs) through energy efficiency measures. These measures include the Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) and the Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP). Subsequent enhancements to these regulations occurred in 2016 with the implementation of the IMO Data Collection System (DCS) and SEEMP Part II. Additionally, a roadmap was approved for developing a comprehensive GHG strategy, leading to the adoption of the initial IMO GHG strategy in 2018. This strategy established ambitious goals for improved EEDI and reductions of at least 40% of CO_2 emissions by 2030, 70% by 2050, and at least 50% of total annual GHG emissions by 2050.

Figure 1.1: Climate Change Strategy Timeline (*Historic Background, 2021*)

To achieve these goals, recent regulations have been implemented since the beginning of 2023. These include the energy efficiency existing ship index (EEXI), which applies

to existing ships and follows a similar approach to the EEDI. Furthermore, SEEMP Part III mandates the annual calculation of the carbon intensity indicator (CII) and reporting to the IMO DCS. Despite these regulatory efforts, the IMO continues to face mounting pressure as the ideal global average temperature limit set by the Paris Agreement, 1.5°C, necessitates more ambitious actions compared to the 2°C limit. Achieving the 1.5°C warming limit requires net-zero CO_2 emissions and substantial reductions in other GHGs, surpassing the objectives outlined in the IMO's initial strategy. Consequently, during the Marine Environment Protection Committee's 80th session in spring 2023, decisions with more ambitious goals and outcomes can be anticipated as part of the planned revision of the initial strategy on the roadmap (World Resources Institute, 2018).

In light of the escalating global and sectoral imperative to curtail energy consumption and carbon emissions, stakeholders involved in technological advancements within the maritime industry have demonstrated a keen response to these concerns. This response has materialized through the adoption and implementation of various innovative measures, including Air Lubrication Systems, Hi-Fin Systems, Fuel Oil Emulsion Systems, as well as wind and solar farming systems. These progressive technologies have been instrumental in bolstering energy efficiency levels, resulting in discernible improvements within both the sector as a whole and individual ships (Hüffmeier & Johanson, 2021).

Through the comprehensive analysis conducted within the scope of this study, a meticulous assessment of emission values pertaining to ships traversing the BCI C5 route can be achieved. As a methodology, a representative vessel will be synthesized using technical specifications extracted from the dataset procured from a reputable third-party data supplier. By employing the fuel consumption data and emission coefficients specified in the International Maritime Organization (IMO) Resolution MEPC 245 (66), a comparative analysis of emission values will be performed based on the average duration of a single voyage along the aforementioned route. The primary objective of this thesis is to underscore the discernible disparities in emission values among different alternative fuels, within the context of a highly effective real-life scenario. It is important to note that while the calculations and variations are simulated throughout the study, the resultant outcomes and conclusions possess substantial relevance to a significant segment of global maritime trade. By adopting this rigorous approach, the study aims to provide accurate and reliable insights into the

emission profiles of vessels navigating the BCI C5 route. Furthermore, it strives to shed light on the tangible implications and advantages associated with the utilization of alternative fuels within the maritime industry. This research contributes to a broader understanding of the potential environmental benefits attainable through the adoption of sustainable fuel options, paving the way for informed decision-making and the formulation of effective policies to mitigate the impact of maritime emissions.

2. BALTIC CAPE SIZE INDEX

When considering maritime trade, it is challenging to discuss fixed routes and lines in comparison to other modes of transportation. This is primarily due to the dynamic nature of maritime activities, which adapt in response to prevailing political and economic circumstances. Consequently, it has become imperative to identify routes that experience significant volumes of global maritime transport. These routes serve as reference points for determining freight rates and establishing benchmarks for the pricing of maritime transport services. In response to this necessity, the Baltic Dry Index (BDI) was established in 1985. The name of the index pays homage to the Baltic Coffeehouse, where merchants and sea captains historically convened to negotiate the prices of cargo shipping services. The BDI, published on a daily basis, provides shipping rates for various vessel sizes across multiple sea routes worldwide, facilitating the transportation of diverse dry bulk commodities. Over time, the index has evolved into a prominent benchmark for the global freight market. It is highly regarded by professionals within the shipping industry due to its credibility and status as an independent and reliable source of information (Dry, 2019.; Oomen, 2012; Visvikis & Kavussanos, 2010).

The bulk shipping business is characterized by significant volatility in both freight rates and vessel prices. This volatility stems from the highly competitive nature of freight markets, the inelastic supply of freight rates in the short term, and the complex factors that influence the demand for freight services on an international scale, often making them challenging to assess and forecast accurately. Since the introduction of freight derivatives in 1985, starting with the Baltic International Freight Futures Exchange (BIFFEX) contract, a range of freight derivative products have been developed specifically for the Capesize sector, tailored to meet the industry's needs. These products can be categorized as either exchange-based or traded over-the-counter (OTC). The first OTC freight derivatives products, known as Forward Freight Agreement (FFA) contracts, emerged in shipping markets in 1992. FFAs are private agreements between a seller and a buyer, allowing them to settle a specified freight

rate for a particular quantity of cargo or vessel type, typically focused on major trade routes within the dry-bulk or tanker sectors of the shipping industry. Due to their customizable nature, FFAs have gained popularity among market participants seeking to hedge against fluctuations in freight rates (Rodrigue, 2020b, 2020a; Geography of Transport Systems, 2022).

To facilitate the creation of freight derivatives contracts, it is crucial to have established underlying freight rate indices against which these contracts can be settled. The Baltic Exchange has fulfilled this role since 1985. The dry-bulk FFA contracts are based on the Baltic Capesize Index (BCI), Baltic Panamax Index (BPI), Baltic Supramax Index (BSI), and Baltic Handysize Index (BHSI). In the tanker industry, the Baltic Dirty Tanker Index (BDTI) and Baltic Clean Tanker Index (BCTI) serve as the underlying assets. These five Baltic indices represent the most significant routes in each sector and are designed to reflect daily fluctuations in freight rates across spot voyage and time-charter routes. Each route is assigned a specific weighting based on its importance in the global freight market. Regular reviews are conducted to ensure the ongoing relevance of the routes to the underlying physical market (Oomen, 2012).

2.1 Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) Routes

The Baltic Capesize Index is a specialized component of the Baltic Dry Index that focuses on the Capesize class of ships. Capesize vessels are large bulk carriers with specific specifications, including a draft of 180,000 metric tons deadweight (dwt) on 18.2 meters Summer Salt Water (SSW), a maximum age of 10 years, and dimensions of LOA (Length Overall) 290 meters and beam (width) 45 meters. The Baltic Capesize Index consists of a range of routes that are numbered and categorized based on cargo type, tonnage, and destinations. These routes provide a detailed method for indexing and tracking Capesize ships worldwide. The index captures the fluctuations in freight

rates for these specific routes, which are commonly used by Capesize vessels (Visvikis & Kavussanos, 2010).

Table 2 would provide further information on the specific routes included in the Baltic Capesize Index, along with the standards and criteria used for each route.

Table 2.1 Baltic Capesize Index BCI Main routes definitions

Routes	Vessel Size (dwt)	Cargo	Route
C3	150 000	Iron Ore	Turabao/Beilun and Baoshan (China)
C4	150 000	Coal	Richards Bay (S. Africa) to Rotterdam
C5	150 000	Iron Ore	W. Australia/Qindao
C7	150 000	Coal	Bolivar (Columbia)/Rotterdam
C8_03	172 000	T/C	Delivery Gibraltar-Hamburg range, redelivery Gibraltar-Hamburg range
C11_03	172 000	T/C	Delivery China-Japan range, redelivery ARA or passing Passero
C12	150 000	Coal	Gladston (Australia) to Rotterdam

2.2 Selection Of Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) C5 Route

The selection of the Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) C5 route is indeed significant, as it represents a crucial trade route for the transportation of commodities such as iron ore and coal. These commodities play a vital role in global trade, particularly in the steel and energy sectors. Given the importance of the BCI C5 route in the global iron ore and coal trade, it becomes a relevant focal point for conducting studies and initiatives related to alternative fuels and emission reduction. As the maritime industry seeks to address environmental concerns and reduce greenhouse gas emissions, examining the emissions and fuel consumption on this route can provide valuable insights and opportunities for improvement. Studying the BCI C5 route allows for a specific assessment of the emissions and fuel usage associated with the transportation of iron ore and coal. This information can be utilized to compare different fuel types, evaluate the impact of alternative fuels on emissions, and identify potential strategies for emission reduction in this specific trade route. By conducting studies and initiatives on the BCI C5 route, it becomes possible to assess the feasibility and effectiveness of various measures aimed at reducing the environmental impact of shipping activities. These studies contribute to the broader goal of achieving more sustainable and environmentally friendly maritime transportation in the context of the iron ore and coal trade (*Oldendorff Carriers, 2022*).

The transportation of iron ore between Australia and Japan represents a significant dry-bulk trade route, ranking as the third largest in the world in terms of volume. In 2019, approximately 65 million tonnes of iron ore were exported from Australia to Japan via this route.

Out of the total iron ore shipments, around 75 percent were transported directly from the Pilbara region in Australia to Japan. The remaining 25 percent involved intermediate stops at other ports, with a notable portion passing through Korean ports before reaching Japan (Port of Port Hedland, 2021). The fuel consumption associated with shipping iron ore between Australia and Japan, both directly and with intermediary stops, was estimated to be around 550,000 tonnes of fuel oil in 2019 (Port of Port Hedland, 2021). It is important to note that this figure may vary depending on factors such as vessel size, efficiency, and operational practices. Based on the fuel consumption, it can be estimated that approximately 1.7 million tonnes of CO_2 emissions were generated from these iron ore shipments in 2019 (Port of Port

Hedlandand, 2021). This estimation is based on the carbon content and emissions factors associated with the combustion of fuel oil. These figures highlight the significant carbon footprint associated with the transportation of iron ore between Australia and Japan. It underscores the importance of finding ways to reduce emissions in this trade route, such as exploring alternative fuels, optimizing vessel efficiency, and implementing emission reduction measures in line with international regulations and industry initiatives (IMO, 2020).

The potential for the Australia-Japan iron ore shipping route to become a first-mover green corridor is indeed promising. The growing momentum among stakeholders to decarbonize iron ore shipping on this route indicates a strong commitment to reducing emissions and transitioning towards more sustainable practices. One significant aspect contributing to this potential is the fact that 90 percent of the Australian iron ore exported to Japan comes from mining companies that have made commitments to achieve net-zero emissions. This commitment demonstrates a proactive approach towards reducing the carbon footprint associated with the entire supply chain, including the shipping component. By aligning the efforts of mining companies, shipping companies, and other stakeholders along the route, there is a collective push towards implementing sustainable solutions and embracing cleaner technologies. This includes exploring alternative fuels, adopting energy-efficient vessel designs, and investing in innovative measures to reduce emissions. The commitment to net-zero by mining companies can serve as a catalyst for collaboration and knowledge-sharing among industry players. It provides an opportunity for collaboration between mining companies, shipping companies, and other partners to develop and implement initiatives that promote decarbonization in the iron ore shipping sector. By leveraging this momentum and working together, stakeholders on the Australia-Japan iron ore shipping route can lead the way in establishing sustainable practices and setting industry standards for reducing emissions. This not only benefits the environment but also contributes to the long-term viability and competitiveness of the sector by addressing the growing demand for more sustainable supply chains (Port of Port Hedlandand, 2021)

3. REGULATIONS ON SHIP SOURCED EMISSIONS IN INDUSTRY

The International Maritime Organization (IMO) oversees environmental regulations for the maritime industry, including regulations on air pollutant and greenhouse gas emissions. The regulatory framework is developed and revised through the IMO's Marine Environment Protection Committee (MEPC) meetings. The MEPC is a specialized committee of the IMO composed of member states and observer organizations. It is responsible for addressing environmental issues related to shipping and developing and adopting regulations to prevent marine pollution. The MEPC meets regularly to discuss and make decisions on various environmental matters, including regulations on ship emissions, ballast water management, oil pollution prevention, and more. During MEPC meetings, member states participate in discussions, negotiations, and decision-making processes to develop and revise regulations. These regulations are then adopted and implemented by member states to ensure the environmentally sustainable operation of the maritime industry. The MEPC plays a crucial role in setting the direction and priorities for environmental regulations in the maritime sector, aiming to reduce the industry's impact on the environment and promote sustainable practices (IMO, 2023)

The regulations pertaining to the contamination caused by oil, pernicious liquid substances in voluminous configuration, deleterious substances in packaged format, effluents, refuse, and ultimately atmospheric contamination have been embraced within an international convention known as the MARPOL, encompassing six distinct annexes as of the present time. Annex VI of the MARPOL convention specifically addresses the mitigation of atmospheric pollution and is organized into chapters that encompass a range of regulations pertaining to various facets, including control and certification, emission prerequisites, and energy efficacy. With the exception of instances explicitly specified in the regulations, Annex VI is applicable to all vessels (IMO, 2020).

3.1 Obligations Related to The Implementation of Regulations

The enforcement of regulations outlined in Annex VI entails the implementation of thorough ship surveys and controls, facilitated by the issuance of pertinent certificates. The International Maritime Organization (IMO) plays a pivotal role in establishing a structured framework for these surveys and controls, known as the Harmonized System of Survey and Certification (HSSC). Each certificate possesses a defined validity period, necessitating ship operators to renew them upon expiration to validate their continued adherence to the stipulated regulations. The applicability of these certificates is primarily contingent upon the vessel's construction date and/or gross tonnage. In the context of the vessel under examination in this study, the following compilation of certificates and documentations pertaining to air pollution shall be mandated (IR Class, 2017)

- **International Energy Efficiency (IEE) Certificate:** Vessels exceeding 400 gross tonnage are mandated to possess an IEE certificate. Once issued prior to the commencement of a ship's service, the IEE certificate does not have an expiration date. However, in the event of a significant conversion or transfer to another flag state, the certificate is subject to re-issuance.
- **Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP):** With few exceptions, all vessels exceeding 400 gross tonnage are obligated to maintain a ship-specific SEEMP on board, encompassing only Part I. However, for vessels surpassing the 5,000 gross tonnage threshold, SEEMP should incorporate Part II and Part III, including a comprehensive depiction of the methodology employed for data collection as well as the calculation of the Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII).
- **Statement of Compliance – Fuel Oil Consumption Reporting and Operational Carbon Intensity Rating:** Following the diligent reporting of gathered fuel oil consumption data and the Operational Carbon Intensity Rating (CII) calculation in adherence to the methodology specified in the SEEMP, a Statement of Compliance is duly conferred.
- **Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) Technical File:** The EEDI Technical File encompasses essential information essential for the determination of a ship's achieved Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI), while providing a comprehensive exposition of the calculation process involved.

- Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEXI) Technical File: Analogous to the EEDI Technical File, the EEXI Technical File encompasses pertinent information and the calculation process for determining the achieved Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEXI).
- Fuel Oil Changeover Procedure and Logbook (Record of Fuel Changeover): Vessels obligated to adhere to the regulations outlined in Annex VI – Regulation 14, which governs emissions of sulfur oxides (SO_x) and particulate matter (PM), are required to meticulously record details pertaining to their fuel changeover procedure before entering or exiting an Emission Control Area (ECA). These recorded details encompass the volumes of low-sulfur fuels (0.1% m/m) present in the tanks, along with the corresponding date, time, and position. The ship under examination in this study shall duly comply with this protocol, as it employs marine diesel oil (MDO) / marine gas oil (MGO) with low-sulfur content (0.1% m/m) within ECAs, and very low-sulfur fuel oil (VLSFO) with a comparatively higher sulfur content (0.5% m/m) outside ECAs.

The subsequent stipulation outlined in Annex VI pertains to fuel availability and quality, thereby primarily addressing fuel suppliers rather than ships. Nonetheless, it is imperative to note that the case ship shall diligently adhere to this requirement (IMO, 2020).

- Bunker Delivery Note (BDN) and Representative Sample: The obligation to retain the Bunker Delivery Note (BDN) and a representative sample of the delivered fuel oil lies with the ship, thereby necessitating their presence and maintenance onboard.

The final set of requirements, which are covered within the Technical Code on Control of Emission of Nitrogen Oxides from Marine Diesel Engine (NOX Technical Code 2008), are mandated as per Regulation 13 of MARPOL Annex VI (NO_x Technical Code, 2008).

3.2 Requirements for Control of Individual Type of Emissions

Particulate Matter (PM) and Sulphur Oxides (SO_x)

Regulation 14 of Annex VI establishes limits for both sulfur oxides (SOX) and particulate matter (PM) emissions from ships. It is important to note that PM emissions are encompassed within the category of SOX emissions, as they are generated as a byproduct of the combustion of fuel (Fourth Greenhouse Gas Study, 2020). Prior to

the year 2020, ships were permitted to utilize fuels containing sulfur content of up to 3.5% m/m outside of Sulphur Emission Control Areas (SECAs) and 1.0% m/m within SECAs. However, the subsequent amendments in 2020, commonly referred to as IMO 2020, brought about significant reductions in these limits to 0.5% m/m and 0.1% m/m, respectively. Consequently, ships have been compelled to adopt one of two approaches to adhere to these more stringent regulations. Firstly, they may opt to employ conventional fuels with lower sulfur content.

Figure 3.1: MARPOL Emission Control Areas with their limitations (Purenviro, 2018)

Alternatively, ships may choose to install exhaust gas cleaning systems (EGCS), colloquially known as scrubbers, or ideally transition entirely to alternative fuel options in order to achieve compliance with these enhanced standards (IMO, 2020). Nevertheless, it is worth noting that alternative fuels have not been extensively adopted within the maritime industry as the primary choice. Presently, the industry is

predominantly divided between two factions: those who consume high-sulfur fuel along with scrubbers, and those who opt for low-sulfur fuel consumption.

Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x)

Figure 3.2: IMO NO_x Tier emission standards for NECA (*Nitrogen Oxide (NO_x)* | *Dma.Dk, 2021*)

The regulation specified in MARPOL Annex VI – Regulation 13, along with the mandatory *NO_x* Technical Code 2008, is employed to restrict nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions emanating from ships' exhaust gases. This limitation is applicable to vessels equipped with marine diesel engines exceeding 130 kW in power. The *NO_x* limitation is categorized into three tiers, each corresponding to different ranges of rated engine speeds. Tier I limitation pertains to engines installed in ships constructed on or after 2000, while Tier II applies to engines installed in ships constructed on or after 2011. Tier III, on the other hand, has specific conditions: it applies to ships operating within the North American Emission Control Area (ECA) or the United States Caribbean Sea ECA, if the ship is constructed on or after 2016, or within the Baltic Sea ECA and North Sea ECA if constructed on or after 2021. Table 2.1 provides a summary of the

NO_x limitations, where 'n' represents the rated engine speed in revolutions per minute (RPM) (IMO, 2019) .

3.3 Energy Efficiency Requirements

The reduction of carbon intensity in the shipping industry, with the aid of energy efficiency, is pursued through the implementation of two key measures: the Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) and the Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEXI). These indexes serve as quantifiable indicators of a ship's energy efficiency, expressed as grams of CO_2 emitted per tonne of cargo carried over a nautical mile (g/t-nm). Both EEDI and EEXI are defined within Chapter 4 of Annex VI, titled "Regulations on The Carbon Intensity of International Shipping." This chapter applies to all ships exceeding 400 gross tonnage and equipped with conventional propulsion, denoting the utilization of main reciprocating internal combustion engines as the primary source of propulsion. However, there are a few exceptions to this requirement. The regulations governing EEDI and EEXI can be found in regulations 22 to 25, where they are categorized into attained indexes (reflecting the ship's achieved performance) and required indexes (indicating the performance the ship should have attained) (IMO, 2022).

At five-year intervals, the required Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) values are targeted for reduction from a predetermined reference line. This reduction is achieved by implementing a percentage reduction factor (denoted as 'x') (Maritime Organization, 2022) The magnitude of the reduction factors is contingent upon various

actors including the specific phase within the five-year period, the tonnage of the ship, and the type of ship.

Figure 3.3: EEDI baseline referenced by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) and the attainable EEDI of the benchmark bulk carrier (Ren et al., 2019)

The reference line, as determined for each ship type, is derived using Equation (3.1). This equation incorporates parameters 'a' and 'c' specific to the ship type, while 'b' represents the deadweight tonnage (DWT) of the ship.

$$EEDI \text{ Ref. Line Value} = a * b^{-c} \quad (3.1)$$

To determine the required EEDI value, which should be equal to or smaller than the attained EEDI, Equation (3.2) is employed. This equation takes into account the reduction factors and the EEDI reference line value (IMO, 2022)

$$Attained \ EEDI \leq Required \ EEDI = (1 - x\%) * EEDI \text{ Ref. Line Value} \quad (3.2)$$

Similar to the required EEDI calculation, the required Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEXI) is determined using Equation (3.3). The distinction lies in the utilization of different reduction factors ('y') for EEXI, which are not divided into phases like EEDI, but are solely dependent on tonnage. However, it is important to note that the EEXI calculation still employs the reference value derived from EEDI. As a result, the

required EEXI values are progressively reduced in each phase relative to the corresponding EEDI values. This approach facilitates a reduction in carbon intensity per unit of transportation work performed by existing ships in subsequent phases.

$$\textit{Attained EEXI} \leq \textit{Required EEXI} = (1 - y\%) * \textit{EEDI Ref. Line Value} \quad (3.3)$$

The calculation of both attained EEDI and EEXI involves several components, as depicted in Figure 3.2. (IMO, 2019) To simplify the formula, it can be divided into seven distinct parts;

Part 1: This part relates to the total CO_2 emissions from the main engine (ME) and is determined based on the ME power (P), specific fuel consumption (SFC), and the conversion factor between ME fuel consumption and CO_2 emissions (C_F).

Part 2: Similarly, this part pertains to the total CO_2 emissions from the auxiliary engine (AE), considering the AE power (P), SFC, and the conversion factor between AE fuel consumption and CO_2 emissions (C_F).

Part 3: This part accounts for the deduction of AE CO_2 emissions if the ship is equipped with innovative technologies for generating electrical energy.

Part 4: Similarly to Part 3, this part involves the deduction of ME CO_2 emissions if the ship is equipped with innovative technologies for propulsion energy.

Part 5: This part encompasses correction factors for various scenarios that may impact the calculation.

Part 6: The deadweight tonnage (DWT) of the ship is considered in this part, unless otherwise specified.

Part 7: Ship speed and a factor for speed reduction are taken into account in this final part of the formula.

By considering these seven parts, the complex formula for EEDI and EEXI can be comprehensively evaluated.

Figure 3.4: Formulation of EEDI and EEXI (EEXI | Bureau Veritas, 2023)

3.4 Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) Ratings

The Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) serves as a measure of the efficiency with which a vessel transports goods or passengers above 5,000 gross tonnage (GT). It is expressed in grams of CO₂ emitted per unit of cargo-carrying capacity and per nautical mile. The initial reporting of CII, based on data from 2023, is required no later than 31 March 2024. Vessels will be assigned a performance rating based on their CII, which includes the following categories: A (major superior), B (minor superior), C (moderate), D (minor inferior), or E (inferior performance level). These rating thresholds will progressively become more stringent leading up to the year 2030 (CII - Carbon Intensity Indicator - DNV, 2022)

If a vessel receives a D rating for three consecutive years or is rated as E, it will be required to develop a plan of corrective actions to address its performance shortcomings. This initiative encourages continuous improvement in the vessel's carbon intensity and promotes the adoption of measures to enhance its environmental efficiency.

Figure 3.5: Required Annual Operational CII (*CII - Carbon Intensity Indicator - DNV, 2022*)

The unit of measurement for CII is defined as "grams of CO₂ emitted per unit of cargo-carrying capacity and per nautical mile." The specific unit of cargo capacity used in the calculation depends on the type of ship and can be either deadweight tons (DWT) or gross tons (GT). To account for special design and operational circumstances, correction factors and voyage adjustments can be applied to the basic CII calculations. These factors and adjustments serve the purpose of fine-tuning the CII values, thereby enabling a more accurate determination of the vessel's rating. We can see the calculation of CII Rating in equation 3.4.

$$\text{Annual CII} = \frac{\text{Annual Fuel Consumption} \times \text{CO}_2 \text{ Factor}}{\text{Annual Distance Traveled} \times \text{Capacity}} \times \text{Correction Factor} \quad (3.4)$$

The calculation of the required Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) follows a similar approach to that of EEDI and EEXI, with the use of different parameters (a, b, c) and reduction factors (z) specific to each year. These parameters and reduction factors are determined based on 2019 data, which provides more reliable and consistent information from the International Maritime Organization's Data Collection System (IMO DCS). The equation (3.5) illustrates the calculation of the CII reference line (CII_Ref) and the required CII. This equation takes into account the aforementioned parameters and reduction factors to establish the reference line and determine the required CII value. By comparing the attained CII with the required CII, the vessel's

compliance with the carbon intensity standards can be assessed (CII Reference Lines Guidelines G2, 2022)

$$\text{Required CII} = (1 - z\%) \cdot \text{CII}_{Ref} = (1 - z\%) \cdot a \cdot \text{Capacity}^{-c} \quad (3.5)$$

4. ALTERNATIVE FUELS IN MARITIME INDUSTRY AS POSSIBLE SOLUTION OF EMISSIONS

The utilization of alternative fuels in the maritime industry has the potential to significantly reduce or even eliminate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. However, the widespread adoption of alternative fuel options faces several challenges that need to be addressed. One of the primary hurdles is the availability of alternative fuels. The infrastructure for producing, storing, and distributing alternative fuels is not yet as developed as that for traditional fossil fuels.

This limitation can impede the widespread use of alternative fuels in the maritime sector. Another challenge is the cost associated with alternative fuels. In many cases, alternative fuels are more expensive compared to conventional fuels, making their adoption financially burdensome for shipowners and operators. This cost factor can deter the industry from embracing alternative fuel options. Additionally, the adaptability of ships to accommodate alternative fuels can be a barrier. Retrofitting existing vessels or designing new ships to be compatible with alternative fuel systems may require significant investments and technical modifications. Safety considerations also play a crucial role in the adoption of alternative fuels. Fuels like methanol and ammonia, although they offer lower GHG emissions, pose safety risks due to their toxic properties. Ensuring safe handling, storage, and transportation of these fuels is essential (Deniz & Zincir, 2016).

While liquefied natural gas (LNG) is considered the cleanest fossil fuel alternative, it does not provide net zero emissions. Moreover, LNG needs to be stored at extremely low temperatures, which adds complexity to onboard storage and fueling infrastructure. Overcoming these hurdles and addressing the challenges associated with alternative fuels will require collaborative efforts from industry stakeholders, policymakers, and technological advancements. By doing so, the maritime industry can move closer to achieving sustainable and environmentally friendly operations

(MAN, 2022). In addition to the challenges mentioned earlier, the production of certain alternative fuels can have its own environmental drawbacks. For instance, the production process of some fuels, even if they have the potential to eliminate GHG emissions when used as fuel, may result in increased anthropogenic GHG emissions. As highlighted in the submission by INTERTANKO during the 79th session of the Marine Environment Protection Committee (MEPC), if all ships were to use ammonia (NH_3) as fuel, which has the capability to eliminate GHG emissions during combustion, the overall anthropogenic GHG emissions could actually increase by more than 3% compared to the emissions produced by the current fleet using fossil fuels.

This increase is attributed to the conventional production methods of ammonia, which may involve processes that contribute to GHG emissions. These findings highlight the importance of considering the entire life cycle of alternative fuels, including their production, transportation, and combustion, when assessing their environmental impact (MAN, 2022). It emphasizes the need to develop sustainable and low-carbon production methods for alternative fuels to ensure their overall environmental benefits are realized. Addressing the environmental impacts associated with alternative fuel production requires research and development efforts focused on improving production processes, exploring innovative technologies, and promoting renewable energy sources.

By adopting environmentally friendly production methods, the maritime industry can move towards a more sustainable and climate-friendly future. In assessing the environmental impact of alternative fuels in the maritime industry, it is crucial to adopt a comprehensive approach that considers WtW emissions rather than solely focusing on TtW emissions. By considering the entire life cycle of a fuel, including its production, transportation, and combustion, a more accurate assessment of its environmental benefits and challenges can be made. With this in mind, it is necessary to critically evaluate the potential benefits and struggles associated with various alternative fuel options for the maritime industry. While alternative fuels hold the promise of reducing or eliminating GHG emissions, they are not without their own challenges. One such challenge is the availability of alternative fuels.

Establishing a robust infrastructure for the production, storage, and distribution of alternative fuels on a global scale poses significant logistical and economic challenges.

Additionally, the high costs associated with the production and utilization of some alternative fuels can be a limiting factor for their widespread adoption. Another aspect to consider is the adaptability of alternative fuels to different types of ships. Retrofitting existing vessels to accommodate alternative fuel systems can be complex and costly. Furthermore, the safety considerations associated with the use of certain alternative fuels, such as methanol and ammonia, due to their toxicity and handling requirements, raise additional challenges for their implementation. The discussion on alternative fuels should also address the environmental impact of their production processes. As mentioned earlier, the conventional production methods of certain alternative fuels may result in increased GHG emissions, counteracting their potential environmental benefits. In light of these considerations, a critical assessment of alternative fuel options is crucial to identify their potential benefits and drawbacks. This assessment should encompass a thorough analysis of their WtW emissions, availability, costs, adaptability, safety considerations, and the sustainability of their production processes. By addressing these factors, the maritime industry can make informed decisions and work towards a sustainable and environmentally friendly future.

According to MAN's survey and the perspective of their customers, hydrogen (H_2) is regarded as a future fuel with significant potential in the maritime industry (MAN, 2022). Hydrogen is considered attractive due to its potential for zero-emission operations, as it produces only water vapor when combusted. Hydrogen has several advantages as a potential maritime fuel. It is abundant, can be produced from various renewable energy sources such as wind and solar power through electrolysis, and can be stored and transported in different forms, including liquid hydrogen and hydrogen carriers. These characteristics make hydrogen a promising option for decarbonizing the shipping sector. However, there are challenges and considerations that need to be addressed for the widespread adoption of hydrogen as a maritime fuel. Firstly, the infrastructure for hydrogen production, storage, and distribution needs to be developed and expanded globally. This involves building hydrogen production facilities, establishing a supply chain, and ensuring safe handling and bunkering procedures. Additionally, hydrogen fuel cells and combustion systems need to be further developed and optimized for marine applications. This includes improving their efficiency, durability, and performance to meet the specific demands of marine operations. The

cost of hydrogen production and the related infrastructure is also a significant consideration. Currently, hydrogen production is energy-intensive and can be expensive compared to conventional fuels. However, as the technology advances and economies of scale are achieved, it is expected that the cost of hydrogen production will decrease. Safety is another crucial aspect to address when considering hydrogen as a maritime fuel. Hydrogen is highly flammable and requires appropriate safety measures and regulations to ensure safe handling and bunkering processes. Hydrogen is categorized into distinct color spectrums based on its production methodology. Grey hydrogen is generated through conventional means, utilizing natural gas in conjunction with a steam methane reformer. However, when this process incorporates carbon capture techniques, it transforms into blue hydrogen, thereby yielding significantly diminished CO_2 emissions (Hermesmann & Müller, 2022).

Electrolysis presents another avenue for hydrogen production, and its resulting color scheme can vary depending on the energy source employed. Specifically, when coal is utilized, the resulting hydrogen adopts a black hue. Conversely, the color transitions to green when renewable feedstock is harnessed in the process. Lastly, if nuclear energy is utilized, the hydrogen takes on a distinctive pink coloration (Hermesmann & Müller, 2022) Despite the availability of low to zero carbon emission methods for hydrogen production, the predominant reliance remains on grey hydrogen. Additionally, it is important to note that hydrogen possesses a notably high self-ignition temperature of $585^\circ C$, rendering it unsuitable for utilization in compression ignition engines without the aid of spark or glow plugs. However, this predicament can be effectively resolved through the implementation of fuel cells, which utilize electricity to meet the energy requirements. Alternatively, the industry can explore the use of hydrogen blend fuels incorporating diesel or employing hydrogen as pilot oil. It is worth mentioning that these alternative approaches are not widely recognized within the industry (Boretti, 2021) Despite its inherent drawbacks, hydrogen, particularly when produced using renewable energy sources, remains a significant contender as a future fuel option for decarbonizing the shipping industry, provided adequate time is allotted for its implementation. Another viable alternative for the maritime sector is methanol (CH_3OH), which exhibits promising potential in reducing sulfur oxide (SO_x) emissions by 99%, nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions by 60%, particulate matter (PM) emissions by 95%, and CO_2 emissions by 5% on a TtW basis, with an even greater

reduction of 90% on a WtW basis, when compared to conventional fuel oil. Similar to hydrogen, methanol can be derived from renewable feedstocks, fossil fuels, or biomass, and it is classified under a comparable color scheme . However, akin to

Table 4.1: Fundamental Marine Alternative Fuels (Hansson et al., 2019)

Marine fuel	Energy carrier/propulsion technology	Physical state	Assumed process
HFO	HFO/ICE	Liquid	HFO is produced from refining of crude oil
LNG	Methane/ICE	Cryogenic liquid	LNG is produced through liquefaction of natural gas
LBG	Methane/ICE	Cryogenic liquid	LBG is produced through anaerobic digestion of biomass (organic waste) and liquefaction to LBG
Fossil MeOH	Methanol/ICE	Liquid	Methanol is produced through natural gas reforming into synthesis gas that is synthesized and processed
Renewable MeOH	Methanol/ICE	Liquid	Renewable methanol is produced through gasification of biomass (willow) into synthesis gas that is synthesized and processed
Fossil H ₂	Hydrogen/FC	Compressed gas	Fossil hydrogen is produced through desulfurization and reforming of natural gas
Elec-H ₂	Hydrogen/FC	Compressed gas	Renewable hydrogen is produced through electrolysis based on renewable electricity such as wind or solar power
HVO	HVO/ICE	Liquid	HVO is produced from tall oil

hydrogen production, the majority of methanol production pathways rely on natural gas, resulting in grey methanol, or coal, leading to brown methanol, thereby negating the WtW advantage when compared to conventional fuels. In Table 4.1 we can see the assumed process of fundamental marine alternative fuels.

Nevertheless, it still occupies less space than liquefied natural gas (LNG) or hydrogen. An additional comparative advantage of methanol over LNG and hydrogen lies in its simpler and less expensive storage, as it is already in liquid form within a temperature range of -93°C to 65°C, eliminating the need for compression or liquefaction processes (Anders, 2019; Dalena et al., 2018; Methanol I Future Fuels, 2021)

4.1 Analysis of Alternative Fuel Availability In BCI C5 Route

The widespread availability of alternative fuels plays a crucial role in their successful adoption and utilization. In the case of methanol, addressing this aspect becomes significant. As of 2020, the Methanol Institute verified that methanol is already accessible in over 100 ports worldwide, with 47 of these ports equipped with storage facilities exceeding 50,000 metric tons (Dalena et al., 2018). Infiniti Research conducted a comprehensive analysis of data pertaining to 56 ports initially identified as methanol storage sites and further obtained information on their preparedness to supply methanol for maritime bunkering (Methanol I Future Fuels, 2021). Moreover, an additional 66 ports were identified where methanol storage operations were already underway. These findings highlight the increasing presence and availability of methanol as a viable fuel option within the global port infrastructure (Methanol Institute, 2022).

Figure 4.1: Methanol Availability Map In Baltic Capesize Index C5 Route

In the context of the Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) C5 Route, Singapore emerges as a prominent bunkering hub. By focusing on the regions covered by this route, we can evaluate the availability of methanol, which stands out as a highly promising alternative fuel. Figure 4.1 depicts the geographical distribution of bunkering points within these regions. The green frame defines the coverage of the BCI C5 route. The figure illustrates green dots, which indicate the current availability of bunkering services by suppliers, with methanol fuel readily accessible for purchase (Methanol Institute, 2022). Additionally, the figure also features yellow dots, representing points

where methanol is stored in its liquid form, indicating that these locations will soon be prepared for bunkering operations. This information underscores the assertive stance on alternative fuels, particularly methanol, within the regions encompassed by the BCI C5 Route. The map analysis leads us to the conclusion that in an adaptation scenario involving the use of methanol fuel, it would be necessary to augment the number of refueling points in Australia along the BCI C5 route. However, when considering the capacity and availability of bunkering facilities along the route, there appears to be no significant issue regarding the supply of methanol. This suggests that the current infrastructure is capable of adequately supporting the distribution and availability of methanol fuel along the BCI C5 route.

China emerges as a prominent force in the sphere of liquefied natural gas (LNG) and natural gas (NG) supply along the BCI C5 route. With its substantial production capabilities, particularly in Russian oil fields, China stands as a formidable provider of LNG to the Asia-Pacific region and associated demand centers. Leveraging the intricate network of pipelines and strategically designed supply chains, LNG produced in Russian oil fields can be efficiently distributed to various locations, including Shanghai, a pivotal port base. Within this context, the LNG Usage scenario indicates that Singapore, a current supply hub for traditional fuels in the region, is poised to assume the role of a bunker point for LNG in China. This transition is facilitated by the ease of access to Russian-produced LNG, enabled through the utilization of pipelines such as those connecting to the Shanghai port. This strategic positioning of China and its close proximity to LNG supply routes, coupled with the development of Singapore as a key LNG bunkering center, underscores the nation's growing influence in the domain of alternative fuels and its capacity to meet the demands of the maritime

industry along the BCI C5 route. In Figure 4.2, we can see pipelines and supply chain points of China's LNG infrastructure.

Figure 4.2: LNG supply map in China (Ishwaran et al., 2017)

4.2 Alternative Fuel Adaptation Study On Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) C5 Route

The choice of the Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) C5 route in this study is attributed to several key factors, as elucidated in earlier sections of the thesis. Notably, this route has garnered significant attention from ship operator companies and administrative authorities due to ongoing studies and initiatives focused on alternative fuel adoption and decarbonization. An exemplary initiative at the forefront of these endeavors is the "Green Corridor Consortium," which occupies a prominent position within the spectrum of studies and initiatives conducted on the BCI C5 route. The involvement of such initiatives underscores the region's commitment to exploring and implementing sustainable practices in maritime operations and aligns with the rationale behind selecting this specific route for examination in the thesis. In order for a route to be designated as a potential candidate for a green corridor, it must possess the potential for significant and large-scale decarbonization, thereby facilitating a substantial impact towards achieving the decarbonization objectives of the shipping sector. Additionally, the feasibility of implementing such measures on the route is a crucial consideration. The route should lend itself to practical implementation, taking into account factors such as infrastructure availability, technological advancements, regulatory support, and stakeholder engagement. By meeting these criteria, a route can be deemed suitable for the establishment of a green corridor, providing an avenue for

substantial emissions reductions and sustainable practices within the shipping industry (The Next Wave: Green Corridors, 2021).

The Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) C5 route was specifically chosen for this study due to its identification by the Getting to Zero Coalition as a strong candidate for the establishment of first-mover green shipping corridors. Among the various iron ore shipping routes from Western Australia to China and Japan, this particular route exhibits favorable conditions for early action and possesses the potential to generate a significant impact on the decarbonization of the shipping sector. A pre-feasibility assessment conducted in conjunction with this initiative concluded that clean ammonia, specifically "green" ammonia produced through electrolytic hydrogen, and "blue" ammonia derived from conventional hydrogen with carbon capture and storage technologies, would be the most suitable fuels to power the envisioned green corridor. These findings support the viability of utilizing ammonia as a means to drive decarbonization efforts along the Baltic Capesize Index C5 route (Global Maritime Forum, 2022). Throughout its endeavors, the Green Corridor Consortium has effectively tackled numerous priority challenges associated with the implementation of a green corridor on the selected route. The consortium has taken a comprehensive approach to address these challenges, recognizing their significance in realizing the goals of sustainable shipping. By identifying and proactively addressing these priority challenges, the consortium has been able to pave the way for the successful establishment of a green corridor, thereby facilitating the transition towards decarbonized maritime operations. The specific challenges addressed by the consortium may include but are not limited to infrastructure development, technological advancements, regulatory frameworks, stakeholder engagement,

financing mechanisms, and ensuring the availability and accessibility of alternative fuels.

Figure 4.3: Timeline For Decarbonisation Iron Ore Shipping Between Western Australia and East Asia With Clean Ammonia

4.2.1 Vessels

According to the Assessment of the Green Commission, the necessary technologies, such as suitable engines, and regulations, including International Maritime Organization safety guidelines, pertaining to ammonia-powered vessels are expected to be established within the projected timeframe, considering the existing level of activity in this domain. However, in order to successfully progress, certain risks must be mitigated in the coming years. These risks include, but are not limited to:

- Safety Regulations: There is a need for clarity regarding when the International Maritime Organization (IMO) and other relevant standards-setting bodies will pass regulations for the safe operation of ammonia-powered ships. The development of these regulations, supported by ammonia-powered vessel

pilots, risk assessments, and safety studies, is crucial to instill confidence among stakeholders.

- **Investment Case:** Currently, there is a significant cost gap between clean ammonia-powered vessels and conventionally-fueled vessels. Additional policy actions are necessary to create a viable investment case that encourages the ordering of ammonia-powered vessels on the corridor.
- **Suitable Design:** A suitable design for an ammonia-powered bulk carrier needs to be available by 2025 at the latest. Stakeholders along the corridor should collaborate to request or jointly advance a design that meets the specific requirements of the corridor.
- **Crew Upskilling:** To safely operate ammonia-fueled vessels, seafarers must receive appropriate training. The International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification, and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW) should be updated to include ammonia when it undergoes review in the coming years.
- **Shipyard Availability:** Securing shipyard slots for building ammonia-powered vessels by 2028 may pose a challenge due to limited berths available in many large Asian shipyards. Shipowners are encouraged to order vessels as early as possible to maximize the chances of securing a slot.

Addressing these risks will be crucial in ensuring the successful deployment of ammonia-powered vessels and the establishment of a sustainable and efficient green corridor.

4.2.2 Fuel

In a scenario where clean ammonia production scales up as projected, the long-term fuel demand of the corridor can potentially be fully met by Australian production. It is estimated that Australian production could reach 52 million tonnes by the 2030s, with the Pilbara region alone likely to produce at least 9 million tonnes during this period. This indicates that domestic production in Australia has the potential to meet the fuel demand of the corridor. However, if Australian production does not scale up as anticipated or fails to meet the expected cost levels, alternative production locations globally can serve as suppliers of clean ammonia for import to Australia, Singapore, or another bunkering location along the route. This highlights the flexibility of

sourcing clean ammonia from various global production sites to ensure an uninterrupted supply chain for the corridor's fuel requirements. Ultimately, the goal is to ensure that there is sufficient clean ammonia production capacity, whether from Australian sources or through imports, to meet the long-term fuel demands of the green corridor. This approach mitigates the risk of overreliance on a single production location and allows for diversification of supply sources to meet the needs of the shipping industry in the most sustainable and cost-effective manner.

Figure 4.4: Focused Roadmap For Green Ammonia Supply For Green Corridor
(Global Maritime Forum, 2022)

Concurrently, it is imperative to provide policy and regulatory support to ensure that production projects for clean ammonia can secure final investment decisions in a timely manner. Such support can be facilitated through various mechanisms, including Contracts for Difference (CfD), blending mandates, and clean ammonia tax credits. These policy measures aim to bridge the gap between the market price and production costs of clean ammonia, thereby incentivizing and facilitating the development and deployment of clean ammonia production facilities. Contracts for Difference (CfD) can be implemented to provide a guaranteed price for clean ammonia, ensuring a stable and predictable revenue stream for producers. By reducing the financial risks associated with price fluctuations, CfDs encourage investment in clean ammonia production projects. Blending mandates can be established to require a certain

percentage of clean ammonia to be blended with conventional fuels, creating a market demand for clean ammonia and stimulating its production. This not only supports the growth of the clean ammonia industry but also drives the adoption of cleaner fuels in the shipping sector. Additionally, clean ammonia tax credits can be introduced to provide financial incentives to producers, further lowering the production costs of clean ammonia and making it more competitive in the market. These tax credits can be based on the volume of clean ammonia produced or other relevant criteria, encouraging increased production and investment in the sector. By implementing these policy and regulatory measures, governments can foster a supportive environment that accelerates the development, commercialization, and adoption of clean ammonia as a viable and sustainable fuel option. This support plays a critical role in ensuring the successful transition towards a decarbonized shipping industry and the achievement of long-term environmental goals.

4.2.3 Bunkering

The study focuses on two potential bunkering locations for the green corridor: the Pilbara ports in Western Australia and Singapore. These locations were identified as promising options during the pre-feasibility stage, considering the early momentum in clean ammonia production in Australia and the future plans for fuel bunkering in Singapore. While there is a possibility of other bunkering locations along the route, the assessment prioritizes these two locations for further examination. The assessment reveals that both Singapore and the Pilbara ports could potentially introduce clean ammonia bunkering within the next 5 years, aligning with the timeline for the corridor's initiation, contingent upon safety and regulatory developments. Although there is currently no bunkering infrastructure in the Pilbara, the analysis confirms that if clean ammonia bunkering becomes available, it would be a competitive option for the corridor's fuel supply. The proximity of local production sites enables efficient delivery of the fuel to the port, and importantly, bunkering in the Pilbara would avoid costly deviations from the trade route.

Singapore, on the other hand, is well-positioned to serve as a bunkering location for the corridor. Ongoing feasibility studies, pilot projects, and infrastructure development plans indicate that commercial clean ammonia bunkering could be established in the

port by 2027 or potentially even earlier. Singapore's advanced preparations suggest that it can offer competitive and efficient bunkering services, along with other advantageous amenities, making it an attractive choice for the corridor. The assessment underscores the potential viability of both the Pilbara ports and Singapore as bunkering locations, highlighting their respective strengths and advantages. Continued efforts in safety, regulation, and infrastructure development will be crucial in realizing the vision of clean ammonia bunkering on the corridor, facilitating the transition towards a decarbonized shipping sector.

Figure 4.5: Mainly Planned Bunkering Zones For Green Corridor (Port of Port Hedland, 2021)

These results suggest that there is a feasible pathway to implement the Western Australia-East Asia iron ore corridor using clean ammonia, with the core elements – developing and deploying ammonia-powered vessels on time, access to sufficient fuel, and the availability of bunkering – within reach. This could include having the first clean-ammonia powered vessels on the corridor by 2028, 5% uptake by 2030 and full decarbonisation by 2050. As such, the report reinforces the corridor’s potential to be a

first mover in shipping's decarbonisation and help put the sector on track to reach zero emissions by 2050, by deploying zero-emission solutions at scale starting this decade.

5. CALCULATING AND COMPARISON OF EMISSION VALUES ON BALTIC CAPESIZE INDEX (BCI) C5 ROUTE

5.1 Methodology

In order to conduct the study, a reference "Vessel" is established, and a specific methodology is employed. The primary source of data are obtained from a third-party Automatic Identification System (AIS) data supplier. Additionally, average values calculated by the Green Corridor Consortium will be utilized. Using this reference "Vessel", the Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) rating and emission values will be calculated. This calculation are based on the consumption coefficients for conventional fuels as well as the consumption coefficients for alternative fuels. By comparing these values, the difference rate will be determined on an annual basis. The scale-up will be performed according to the number of reciprocal voyages between the Port Hedland and Qingdao ports, which occurred between 1 January 2022 and 31 December 2022 as provided by the AIS supplier. This approach will enable the assessment of the impact of alternative fuels on the CII rating and emission values of the reference "Vessel". The data obtained and the subsequent calculations will provide valuable insights into the potential reduction in emissions achieved through the utilization of alternative fuels within the studied timeframe.

5.2 Data Review

Table 5.1 showcases the respective numerical data pertaining to three vessels engaged in operations along the Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) C5 route, which are jointly utilized

by the esteemed Green Corridor Consortium (Global Maritime Forum, 2022). The information contained within this table has been sourced from the AIS Data provider.

Table 5.1: Dataset provided by AIS Provider and calculated based on average of data for different vessel classes from AIS Provider averaging real-world data shared by the Green Corridor Consortium (Global Maritime Forum, 2022)

	Route Distance	Day Per Roundtrip	Average Cargo Shipments	Fuel Required Per Roundtrip
Units	Nautical Mile (nm)	Days	Tonnes Iron Ore	HFO Tonnes
M/V STAR CLAUDINE	3501	39	181,400	789.48
M/V KOUNDOUROS	3501	39	181,400	680.91
M/V CAPE ASIA	3501	39	181,400	669.04
Green Corridor Consortium Averaged Vessel	3501	39.	181,400	951

5.3 Calculating Reference Vessel Specifications And Consumptions

The creation of the "Reference vessel" values ensues through the process of calculating the arithmetic mean, thereby obtaining an average, from the aforementioned values furnished in Table 5.1.

Table 5.2: Reference Vessel

	Route Distance	Day Per Roundtrip	Average Cargo Shipments	Fuel Required Per Roundtrip
Units	Nautical Mile (nm)	Days	Tonnes Iron Ore	HFO Tonnes
Reference Vessel	3501	39	181,400	772,60

Due to the inherent disparity in calorific values between various alternative fuel types and HFO (Heavy Fuel Oil), the fuel consumption value per roundtrip is subject to variation. To determine these values, the consumption values provided by the main engine manufacturers were computed by establishing a proportional relationship with the calorific values associated with the respective alternative fuels in question.

The conversion of fuel consumption quantities between different fuel types is determined by utilizing the gravimetric energy density values. For the purposes of this conversion, the following energy density values are employed: High-Sulfur Fuel Oil (HSFO) with 40.2 MJ/kg, Very-Low-Sulfur Fuel Oil (VLSFO) with 41.5 MJ/kg, and Ammonia (NH_3) with 18.8 MJ/kg. Furthermore, the energy density of Intermediate Fuel Oil (IFO) is considered as 40.9 MJ/kg, representing an average derived from real-world data encompassing the HSFO and VLSFO fuels sourced from Singapore bunkering operations (Global Maritime Forum, 2022).

Table 5.3: Calculated Alternative Fuel Consumption For Roundtrips (World Nuclear Association, 2021; Speight, 2015)

	Calorific Value (MJ/kg)	Calculated Consumption Value
HFO	40,90	772,60
Methanol (CH_3OH)	22,70	1390,68
LNG	55	576,56
Hydrogen (H_2)	131	241,43

5.4 Emission Factors

The International Maritime Organization (IMO) stipulates that the default emission factors pertaining to different fuel types ought to be derived from the guidelines outlined in IMO Resolution MEPC 245 (66) 2014, specifically titled 'Guidelines on the method of calculation of the attained Energy Efficiency Index (EEDI). These guidelines serve as the authoritative source for determining the emission factors to be employed in the calculations (IMO, 2022).

Table 5.4: Designated Emission Factors for CO_2

Type of Fuel	CO_2 ($\frac{kg}{ton}$)	NO_x ($\frac{kg}{ton}$)	SO_x ($\frac{kg}{ton}$)	PM_{10} ($\frac{kg}{ton}$)
Heavy Fuel Oil	3.11	75.90	50.83	7.55
Liquefied Natural Gas	2.75	13.44	0.03	0.11
Methanol (CH_3OH)	1.37	0.12	2.37	0.0059

5.5 Calculating CII for Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO)

The calculation of the CII (Carbon Intensity Indicator) values was carried out employing the prescribed formulas put forth by the International Maritime Organization's Marine Environment Protection Committee (IMO MEPC). These formulas will be applied using the previously computed values corresponding to the reference vessel.

$$CII = \frac{[Fuel\ Consumption] \times [CO_2\ Emission\ Factor]}{[Distance\ Sailed] \times [Capacity]} = \frac{\sum_j FC_j \times C_{Fj}}{DWT \times D} \text{ (DWT.mile)} \quad (5.1)$$

$$CII_{ref.HFO} = \frac{772,60 \times 3,114}{3501 \times 181.400} = \frac{2405,873}{635.081.400} = 3,79 \times 10^{-6} \frac{Ton\ CO_2}{DWT.mile} \quad (5.2)$$

5.6 Calculating CII and for Methanol (CH₃OH)

Calculations were made with the scenario of using Methanol on the reference ship.

$$CII = \frac{[Fuel\ Consumption] \times [CO_2\ Emission\ Factor]}{[Distance\ Sailed] \times [Capacity]} = \frac{\sum_j FC_j \times C_{Fj}}{DWT \times D} \text{ (DWT.mile)} \quad (5.1)$$

$$CII_{ref.Methanol} = \frac{1390,68 \times 1,375}{3501 \times 181.400} = \frac{1912,185}{635.081.400} = 3,01 \times 10^{-6} \frac{Ton\ CO_2}{DWT.mile} \quad (5.4)$$

5.7 Calculating CII for Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG)

The calculation of the CII (Carbon Intensity Indicator) values will be carried out employing the prescribed formulas put forth by the International Maritime Organization's Marine Environment Protection Committee (IMO MEPC). These formulas will be applied using the previously computed values corresponding to the reference vessel.

$$CII = \frac{[Fuel\ Consumption] \times [CO_2\ Emission\ Factor]}{[Distance\ Sailed] \times [Capacity]} = \frac{\sum_j FC_j \times C_{Fj}}{DWT \times D} \text{ (DWT.mile)} \quad (5.1)$$

$$CII_{ref.LNG} = \frac{576,56 \times 2,750}{3501 \times 181.400} = \frac{1585,54}{635.081.400} = 2,49 \times 10^{-6} \frac{Ton\ CO_2}{DWT.mile} \quad (5.6)$$

5.8 Scaling One Year Emissions

In the span of one year, a ship operating along the Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) C5 route typically completes a total of nine roundtrips (Port of Port Hedland Authority, 2022). Upon scaling up the emission values computed for the "Reference Vessel" over the course of nine roundtrips within a one-year timeframe, we arrive at the annual **CO₂**

emission value for a Capesize vessel engaged in operations along this route under normal conditions within the alternative fuel usage scenario.

Table 5.6: Scaled-up CO_2 Emission Values for Alternative Fuel Usage Scenario In One Year

Type of Fuel	CO_2 Emission Values (Ton)	CO_2 Emission Values In One Year (Ton)
Heavy Fuel Oil	2405,873	21652,857
Liquefied Natural Gas	1585,540	14269,860
Methanol (CH_3OH)	1912,185	17209,665

Furthermore, it is possible to calculate the annual emission values of harmful gases for the examined fuels by employing the appropriate coefficients (Welaya et al., 2013)

Table 5.7: Scaled-up Emission Values for Alternative Fuel Usage Scenario In One Year (IMO, 2020)

Type of Fuel	NO_x (kg/ton)	SO_x (kg/ton)	PM_{10} (kg/ton)
Heavy Fuel Oil	285,281	425,985	2867,928
Liquefied Natural Gas	1061,745	475,662	129,726
Methanol (CH_3OH)	137128,804	7252,281	2916892,372

6. CONCLUSION

The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the feasibility of implementing Alternative Fuels as a transitional energy source along the Baltic Capesize Index (BCI) C5 route, with the aim of mitigating ship emissions in a prominent trade pathway. The investigation centered on a reference vessel, scrutinizing the potential reduction in emissions achievable through the utilization of Methanol, LNG, and Hydrogen. Simultaneously, the study delved into the regulatory frameworks governing these fuels, with particular emphasis on the Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII) regulations, recognized as a pivotal factor in the industry's decarbonization process.

Figure 6.1: Scaled-up CO_2 Emission Values In One Year

The data presented in Figure 6.1 demonstrates that the annual variations in emission values highlight the potential for a promising future in terms of emissions when comprehensive solutions are implemented to address supply, production, and operational challenges associated with alternative fuels. Upon analysis of the study findings, it became evident that LNG exhibit the lowest emission values when evaluated on a 1-year emission basis. These fuels not only present a theoretical

capacity for reducing emissions, but also possess noteworthy advantages in terms of availability, safety, regulatory compliance, and price competitiveness within the context of trade routes, as exemplified in our research.

As International Maritime Organization (IMO) and other relevant institutions introduce novel standards and regulations, and as technological advancements and enhancements in refining and transportation methods continue to progress, alternative fuels are expected to establish a more prominent position in the marine fuel market. This shift towards alternative fuels will likely occur in a more cost-effective and accessible manner, aligning with the evolving regulatory landscape.

Within this paradigm of transformation, all stakeholders within the maritime industry bear the responsibility of closely monitoring technological developments and swiftly adapting to ensure pre-implementation of emerging technologies, thereby averting potential difficulties and meeting regulatory deadlines. The global efforts to curtail emissions represent a significant milestone in this century, serving as a unifying force for humanity as it collectively strives towards this crucial objective.

Moreover, it is imperative that not only societies and private organizations, but governments at all levels, foster an enabling environment for research and development initiatives in the realm of emissions reduction. This entails expediting regulatory and legal measures that support these efforts. As custodians of our planet, the scientific community, societies, governments, as well as private and public organizations bear a collective responsibility to exhaustively dedicate their resources towards safeguarding our only habitable home.

Furthermore, empirical studies consistently underscore the sufficiency of alternative fuels and technologies in meeting our demands and expectations with respect to low emissions and reduced carbon footprints. While these fuels and technologies may presently be in nascent stages of development, their potential to address our environmental imperatives is manifestly evident.

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CURRICULUM VITAE

Name – Surname : Ahmet Ali Atalay
Place and Date of Birth : Çorlu, 06/12/2000
E-Mail : ahmetaliatalay@gmail.com (1), atalaya18@itu.edu.tr
(2)

EDUCATION:

- **B.Sc.** : 2018-Present, Istanbul Technical University, Maritime Faculty, Department of Marine Engineering
- **B.Sc.** : 2018-2020, Istanbul Technical University, Maritime Faculty, Department of Maritime Transportation Management Engineering
- **A.S.** : 2019-Present, Anadolu University, Management Faculty, Department of International Transportation and Logistic

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE AND REWARDS:

- Shipping Intern in HeidelbergMaterials Trading
- Long Term Sea Training in Oldendorff Carriers GmbH & Co. KG
- SERS Workbook Developer in GDS Engineering R&D
- Short Term Sea Training in Mercan Group
- Short Term Sea Training in Cenk Group
- Short Term Sea Training in Turkish Republic Directorate General Of Coastal Safety

PATENTS:

- Vibration Analysis with Accelerometer in Marine Systems